

BIBLIOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM

Journal Full Title: [Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences](#)

Journal NLM Abbreviation: J Biomed Res Environ Sci

Journal Website Link: <https://www.jelsciences.com>

Journal ISSN: 2766-2276

Category: Multidisciplinary

Subject Areas: Medicine Group, Biology Group, General, Environmental Sciences

Topics Summation: 130

Issue Regularity: [Monthly](#)

Review Process: [Double Blind](#)

Time to Publication: 21 Days

Indexing catalog: [Visit here](#)

Publication fee catalog: [Visit here](#)

DOI: 10.37871 ([CrossRef](#))

Plagiarism detection software: [iThenticate](#)

Managing entity: USA

Language: English

Research work collecting capability: Worldwide

Organized by: [SciRes Literature LLC](#)

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Manuscript should be submitted in Word Document (.doc or .docx) through

Online Submission

form or can be mailed to support@jelsciences.com

**IndexCopernicus
ICV 2020:
53.77**

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CASE REPORT

Drinking Water Containing Platinum-Palladium (Functional Nutrient Water) Improved Interstitial Pneumonia and COPD: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

In this case, when a patient with interstitial pneumonia was given platinum palladium, improvement in respiratory function was observed. Generally, various treatment methods are used for interstitial pneumonia, but conservative therapy has been the main focus and no curative solution has been reached. In this case, there was a tendency for improvement in patients who took platinum palladium, so we reported it. Since it is only drunk, it is not invasive and has great benefits for patients. It has also been reported that COPD, which is also a respiratory disease, showed an improvement tendency by drinking platinum palladium. Although the mechanism is still unknown, it is considered that it is largely due to the antioxidant action by platinum palladium and the activation of AMPK. In the future, we would like to examine further cases and improve the mechanism.

Introduction

Interstitial pneumonia is a general term for diseases in which inflammation occurs mainly in the stroma of the lung [1]. The alveolar is roughly divided into parenchyma and stroma, the inside of the alveolar is called parenchyma, the wall of the alveolar and surrounding tissues are called stroma, and the disease that causes inflammation in this stroma is called interstitial pneumonia [2]. The causes of interstitial pneumonia include "autoimmune interstitial pneumonia", "occupational environmental interstitial pneumonia", and "medicinal interstitial pneumonia" causes [3-5]. Those that cannot be identified are referred to as "idiopathic interstitial pneumonia" [6]. In addition, interstitial pneumonia was classified by ATS / ERS in 2013.

1) Major IIPs

1. Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis (IPF)
2. Idiopathic Nonspecific Interstitial Pneumonia (idiopathic NSIP)

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DOI: 10.37871/jbres1498

Submitted: 10 June 2022

Accepted: 13 June 2022

Published: 15 June 2022

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OPEN ACCESS

Keywords

- > Functional nutrient water
- > Platinum-palladium
- > Interstitial pneumonia
- > COPD
- > AMPK

MEDICINE GROUP

PULMONOLOGY | RESPIRATORY MEDICINE

VOLUME: 3 ISSUE: 6 - JUNE, 2022

How to cite this article: Kawakami S, Shirakawa T, Sakabe K, Sato T, Ide T, Wajima S, Suma R, Fukuzawa Y. Drinking Water Containing Platinum-Palladium (Functional Nutrient Water) Improved Interstitial Pneumonia and COPD: A Case Report. J Biomed Res Environ Sci. 2022 June 10; 3(6): 688-693. doi: 10.37871/jbres1498, Article ID: JBRES1498, Available at: <https://www.jelsciences.com/articles/jbres1498.pdf>

3. Respiratory Bronchiolitis Interstitial Lung Disease (RB-ILD)
4. Desquamative Interstitial Pneumonia (DIP)
5. Cryptogenic Organizing Pneumonia (COP)
6. Acute Interstitial Pneumonia (AIP)

2) Rare IIPs

1. Idiopathic Lymphoid Interstitial Pneumonia (LIP)
2. Idiopathic Pleuroparenchymal Fibroelastosis (PPFE)

3) Unclassifiable

1. Unclassifiable IIPs

It is said to be 9 categories [7].

In this case, there was a tendency for improvement in patients with Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis (IPF). In interstitial pneumonia, the alveolar wall gradually becomes fibrotic due to inflammation [8], and the Pulmonary Surfactant Protein-D (SP-D) rises [9,10]. As alveolar function declines, it becomes difficult to take in oxygen by inhalation, so symptoms such as breathlessness and coughing have been confirmed, and it has been pointed out that it may eventually lead to respiratory failure [11]. At present, there is no effective treatment method, and either antifibrotic therapy for IPF or immunosuppressive therapy for non-IPF ILD is used as symptomatic therapy [12].

On the other hand, COPD is an abbreviation for Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease and is a type of chronic respiratory disease. COPD is a disease characterized by shortness of breath by causing destruction and inflammation of the alveolar, and also with coughing and sputum, which progresses irreversibly. Most COPD originates from smoking, but some may also be caused by environmental impact [13,14]. As with interstitial pneumonia, no effective treatment method has been established for COPD, and it is said that there is no choice but to inhale oxygen and maintain/promote QOL in conservative therapy [15]. Epidemiologically, it is said to be the third leading cause of death in the world as predicted by WHO by 2030 [16]. Epidemiological studies have also suggested that COPD has a high risk of developing lung cancer [17]. Until now, quitting, antioxidants, diets, and alternative therapies have been the main focus for COPD [18], but these have been aimed at slowing the progression. Dr. Taro Shirakawa of Japan reported that when platinum palladium was administered to patients with COPD, there was a tendency for improvement in approximately 40 to 50% of patients. In this case, it was expected that the same therapeutic effect would be obtained for interstitial pneumonia, so the case was examined.

Platinum-palladium is sold as PAPLAL® as a refreshing drinking water (functional nutrient water) in Japan, which is a solution of platinum and palladium mixed at a ratio of 1:3. The idea was by Hideyo Noguchi, a Japanese doctor (Figures 1,2). It is a completely new nutrient water that is expected

to have various effects such as induction of apoptosis in gastric cancer and colon cancer and activation of NK cells (No submission).

Platinum is a chemically extremely stable element and is used for various purposes. In the medical field, the complex is used as an anticancer agent [19]. Other utilization methods focusing on the antioxidant effect of platinum have been reported [20]. Palladium is one of the platinum group elements and is widely used as a material for industrial products and dental treatment [21,22]. In addition, it has been reported that palladium has the effect of imparting reducing power to platinum involved in the reduction reaction again [23], and attempts have been made to utilize a substance in which platinum and palladium are mixed [24]. Due to the chemical reaction and specificity of these two elements, a mixture of platinum and palladium is expected to be useful as a substance with sustained antioxidant capacity compared to the case of platinum alone [24]. Furthermore, it is known that platinum palladium moderately removes all four types of active oxygen [25]. As far as the literature is concerned, there is no other substance that removes all four types of active oxygen (generally four types: superoxide anion radical, hydroxyl radical, hydrogen peroxide, and single-term oxygen [26]. In addition, platinum palladium

Figure 1 Platinum colloid.

Figure 2 Palladium colloid.

is said to have a low absorption rate in the intestinal tract due to its characteristics [27,28], and by acting as a catalyst and acting on cells in each organ in the digestive tract, AMPK (AMP-activated protein kinase) At the same time, it may be said that it contributes to the improvement of interstitial pneumonia and COPD. Therefore, this time, along with the case report, we also confirmed at the in vitro level whether platinum palladium activates AMPK.

Case

Target person

Man in their 88 years old.

Height 172 cm, weight 68 kg, Body surface area 1.800 m2

- Smoking history: NONE
- Current disease: Interstitial pneumonia
- Interstitial pneumonia onset age: 85 years. (As of 2020)
- Underlying disease: NONE
- Platinum & Palladium intake: 18 ml/day (6 ml/1 vial x 3 vial)
- Duration: 11 months
- Treatment with medicine: NONE

Respiratory function test results (28/04/22)

SVC	Measured Value
VC (L)	2.63
ERV (L)	1.32
IRV (L)	0.75
TV (L)	0.56
IC (L)	1.31
FVC (L)	2.50
FEV1.0 (L)	2.02
FEV1.0% (G) (%)	80.80
FEV1.0% (T) (%)	76.81
PEF (L/a)	2.82
V75 (L/a)	2.80
V50 (L/a)	2.39
V25 (L/a)	1.07
V25/HT (L/a)	0.62
MMF (L/a)	2.08

Progress

This man walked 2-3 km every day to maintain and improve his health in his daily life. He has no history of smoking and has a history of drinking. Suddenly, coughing was frequently confirmed, and although a cough suppressant was prescribed, there was no improvement. Upon re-examination at the city hospital, findings peculiar to interstitial pneumonia were confirmed by examinations

such as chest X-ray photographs. He was diagnosed with interstitial pneumonia. He is sentenced to two more years to live. He gradually progresses, and even in the daily activities of climbing the stairs at home and going to the toilet, he has difficulty breathing and collapses. He lost his energy to move, but by drinking platinum palladium, he improved his respiratory function on the 18th day. Coughing stopped and breathing difficulty decreased. At this stage, improvements have been seen before walking can be resumed. However, it is considered necessary to continue to take platinum-palladium because respiratory distress occurred again when platinum-palladium was suspended for a period of time.

AMPK measurement

Examination of AMPK activity by platinum palladium:

In this experiment, CycLex[®] AMPK Kinase Assay Kit (MEDICAL & BIOLOGICAL LABORATORIES CO., LTD. Tokyo, Japan) was used as usual, and the PBS-added group was used for the AMPK activity in the platinum-palladium-added group (final concentration 1%). A purchased human breast cancer cell line (MCF-7) was used as a control for comparative evaluation. In this kit, in order to measure the current activity of AMPK, the activity of AMPK was confirmed 1 hour, 12 hours, and 24 hours after the addition. In addition, the evaluation was statistically evaluated by the Mann-Whitney U test using statistical processing software (IBM SPSS Statistics Ver.26).

Results

When platinum palladium was administered to MCF-7 and the activity of AMPK was measured, it was confirmed that the activity was significantly increased at a significance level of 1% in all groups when the control group was set to 100% (Table 1, figure 3).

Discussion

This report is a case in which platinum palladium was able to approach interstitial pneumonia. Platinum palladium has been suggested to be an effective treatment for interstitial pneumonia. Currently, treatment for interstitial pneumonia is being carried out with a focus on conservative therapy, with the intention of not exacerbating it, but it is difficult to improve. However, in this case, improvement in daily life movements was observed, so it is possible that lung function may be improved. The mechanism is still largely unknown, but we considered the possibility. Although the cause of interstitial pneumonia is often unknown, it causes inflammation in the stroma, so it is possible that active oxygen is produced [29]. Active oxygen releases inflammatory cytokines and has a good side as a defense system, while excess active oxygen adversely affects normal cells, causing lifestyle diseases, aging and chronic inflammation. Is known [30,31]. Platinum palladium was used in this case, but since platinum palladium causes moderate antioxidants as described above, it is possible that

Table 1: Absorbance of hourly control group and Platinum & Palladium colloid-added group.

1. Absorbance					
1 hr		12 hrs		24 hrs	
Cnt	Pt:Pd	Cnt	Pt:Pd	Cnt	Pt:Pd
0.285 ± 0.013	2.308 ± 0.223	0.352 ± 0.019	2.689 ± 0.447	0.264 ± 0.034	2.341 ± 0.082
2. AMPK activity increase rate when cnt is 100%					
1 hr		12 hrs		24 hrs	
Cnt	Pt:Pd	Cnt	Pt:Pd	Cnt	Pt:Pd
100%	809.80%	100%	763.92%	100%	886.74%

Figure 3 Rate of increase in AMPK activity in the control group and Platinum & Palladium colloid -added group at each time. (Mann-Whitney U test. $p < 0.01$).

only the unnecessary active oxygen was removed without removing the necessary active oxygen. It is possible that this led to the improvement of interstitial pneumonia. When the activity of AMPK by platinum-palladium was confirmed at the in vitro level, the AMPK activity was confirmed at a significant level of 1% in all groups. AMPK (AMP-activated protein kinase) is an energy sensor in the body and is a serine / threonine kinase that works to maintain the homeostasis of sugar and lipid metabolism [32]. It is said that activation of AMPK regulates energy metabolism and maintains energy constancy, and is attracting attention as a potential therapeutic effect for metabolic diseases including type 2 diabetes and cancer [32]. The existence of energy is indispensable for human beings to live, and the energy source is ATP (adenosine triphosphate), and when ATP is hydrolyzed and converted to ADP (adenosine diphosphate) occurs [33]. By regulating this ATP level, AMPK is expected to maintain homeostasis and be effective against metabolic diseases such as cancer, type II diabetes, and obesity [34-36]. It is considered that AMPK regulates metabolism by inhibiting the ATP consumption pathway [37,38]. Therefore, AMPK contributes to the maintenance of health in the living body by suppressing chronic inflammation [39,40] promote autophagy [41]. It enhances mitochondrial function [42] and may increase intracellular ATP levels by activating mitochondrial biosynthesis [43,44].

In other words, it is considered that the prevention

of lifestyle diseases including cancer can be expected by increasing the activity of AMPK. It is thought that AMPK regulates metabolism by inhibiting the ATP consumption pathway. It has been reported that AMPK activity reduces abnormal inflammatory reactions and cell aging, leading to treatment of interstitial pneumonia [45], and it is said that platinum palladium will play a part in improving interstitial pneumonia by utilizing its action. The possibility was suggested.

Acknowledgment

I would also like to express our deep gratitude to Dr. Kou Sakabe of Chiba University, Center for Preventive Medical Sciences and Dr. Yoshitaka Fukuzawa of Aichi Medical University for his useful advice in conducting this research.

Ethical considerations

This case was approved by the Ethics Review Committee of the Hino Welfare Clinic (Tokyo, Japan). (HKC_N10022022)

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Lamb YN. Nintedanib: A Review in Fibrotic Interstitial Lung Diseases. *Drugs*. 2021 Apr;81(5):575-586. doi: 10.1007/s40265-021-01487-0. Epub 2021 Mar 25. Erratum

in: *Drugs*. 2021 Apr 13; [Erratum in: *Drugs*. 2021 Jun;81(9):1133. PMID: 33765296; PMID: PMC8163683.

2. Renzoni EA, Poletti V, Mackintosh JA. Disease pathology in fibrotic interstitial lung disease: is it all about usual interstitial pneumonia? *Lancet*. 2021 Oct 16;398(10309):1437-1449. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(21)01961-9. Epub 2021 Sep 6. PMID: 34499865.
3. Graney BA, Fischer A. Interstitial Pneumonia with Autoimmune Features. *Ann Am Thorac Soc*. 2019 May;16(5):525-533. doi: 10.1513/AnnalsATS.201808-565CME. PMID: 30695649; PMID: PMC6850782.
4. Reynolds C, Feary J, Cullinan P. Occupational Contributions to Interstitial Lung Disease. *Clin Chest Med*. 2020 Dec;41(4):697-707. doi: 10.1016/j.ccm.2020.08.015. PMID: 33153688.
5. Renzoni EA, Poletti V, Mackintosh JA. Disease pathology in fibrotic interstitial lung disease: is it all about usual interstitial pneumonia? *Lancet*. 2021 Oct 16;398(10309):1437-1449. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(21)01961-9. Epub 2021 Sep 6. PMID: 34499865.
6. Belloli EA, Beckford R, Hadley R, Flaherty KR. Idiopathic non-specific interstitial pneumonia. *Respirology*. 2016 Feb;21(2):259-68. doi: 10.1111/resp.12674. Epub 2015 Nov 13. PMID: 26564810.
7. American Thoracic Society; European Respiratory Society. American Thoracic Society/European Respiratory Society International Multidisciplinary Consensus Classification of the Idiopathic Interstitial Pneumonias. This joint statement of the American Thoracic Society (ATS), and the European Respiratory Society (ERS) was adopted by the ATS board of directors, June 2001 and by the ERS Executive Committee, June 2001. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2002 Jan 15;165(2):277-304. doi: 10.1164/ajrccm.165.2.ats01. Erratum in: *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2002 Aug 1;166(3):426. PMID: 11790668.
8. Maher TM, Wuyts W. Management of Fibrosing Interstitial Lung Diseases. *Adv Ther*. 2019 Jul;36(7):1518-1531. doi: 10.1007/s12325-019-00992-9. Epub 2019 May 22. PMID: 31119691; PMID: PMC6824393.
9. Takahashi H, Fujishima T, Koba H, Murakami S, Kurokawa K, Shibuya Y, Shiratori M, Kuroki Y, Abe S. Serum surfactant proteins A and D as prognostic factors in idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis and their relationship to disease extent. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2000 Sep;162(3 Pt 1):1109-14. doi: 10.1164/ajrccm.162.3.9910080. PMID: 10988138.
10. Chiba H, Otsuka M, Takahashi H. Significance of molecular biomarkers in idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis: A mini review. *Respir Investig*. 2018 Sep;56(5):384-391. doi: 10.1016/j.resinv.2018.06.001. Epub 2018 Jul 17. PMID: 30030108.
11. Brasch F. Interstitielle Lungenerkrankungen [Interstitial pulmonary diseases]. *Pathologe*. 2006;27(2):116-132.
12. Wong AW, Ryerson CJ, Guler SA. Progression of fibrosing interstitial lung disease. *Respir Res*. 2020 Jan 29;21(1):32. doi: 10.1186/s12931-020-1296-3. PMID: 31996266; PMID: PMC6988233.
13. Turin GM. Natural history and clinical management of emphysema in patients with and without Alpha1-Antitrypsin inhibitor deficiency. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*. 1991;624(1):18-29.
14. Tashkin DP, Detels R, Simmons M, Liu H, Coulson AH, Sayre J, Rokaw S. The UCLA population studies of chronic obstructive respiratory disease: XI. Impact of air pollution and smoking on annual change in forced expiratory volume in one second. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 1994 May;149(5):1209-17. doi: 10.1164/ajrccm.149.5.8173761. PMID: 8173761.
15. Stoller JK, Panos RJ, Krachman S, Doherty DE, Make B; Long-term Oxygen Treatment Trial Research Group. Oxygen therapy for patients with COPD: current evidence and the long-term oxygen treatment trial. *Chest*. 2010 Jul;138(1):179-87. doi: 10.1378/chest.09-2555. PMID: 20605816; PMID: PMC2897694.
16. Organization WH. World health statistics 2010. World Health Organization, Geneva, 2010.
17. Young RP, Hopkins RJ, Christmas T, Black PN, Metcalf P, Gamble GD. COPD prevalence is increased in lung cancer, independent of age, sex and smoking history. *Eur Respir J*. 2009 Aug;34(2):380-6. doi: 10.1183/09031936.00144208. Epub 2009 Feb 5. PMID: 19196816.
18. Fischer BM, Voynow JA, Ghio AJ. COPD: balancing oxidants and antioxidants. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis*. 2015 Feb 2;10:261-76. doi: 10.2147/COPD.S42414. PMID: 25673984; PMID: PMC4321570.
19. Moreira-Pais A, Ferreira R, Gil da Costa R. Platinum-induced muscle wasting in cancer chemotherapy: Mechanisms and potential targets for therapeutic intervention. *Life Sci*. 2018 Sep 1;208:1-9. doi: 10.1016/j.lfs.2018.07.010. Epub 2018 Jul 6. PMID: 30146014.
20. Katarzyna M, Anna S, Zielinska-Blizniewska H, Ireneusz M. An Evaluation of the Antioxidant and Anticancer Properties of Complex Compounds of Copper (II), Platinum (II), Palladium (II) and Ruthenium (III) for Use in Cancer Therapy. *Mini Rev Med Chem*. 2018;18(16):1373-1381. doi: 10.2174/1389557518666180423145825. PMID: 29692246.
21. Lee SJ, Yu Y, Jung HJ, Naik SS, Yeon S, Choi MY. Efficient recovery of palladium nanoparticles from industrial wastewater and their catalytic activity toward reduction of 4-nitrophenol. *Chemosphere*. 2021 Jan;262:128358. doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.128358. Epub 2020 Sep 15. PMID: 33182147.
22. Ucar Y, Brantley WA, Bhattiprolu SN, Johnson WM, McGlumphy EA. Characterization of cast-to implant components from five manufacturers. *J Prosthet Dent*. 2009 Oct;102(4):216-23. doi: 10.1016/S0022-3913(09)60156-6. PMID: 19782823.
23. Okamoto H, Horii K, Fujisawa A, Yamamoto Y. Oxidative deterioration of platinum nanoparticle and its prevention by palladium. *Exp Dermatol*. 2012 Jul;21 Suppl 1:5-7. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-0625.2012.01494.x. PMID: 22626463.
24. Shibuya S, Ozawa Y, Watanabe K, Izuo N, Toda T, Yokote K, Shimizu T. Palladium and platinum nanoparticles attenuate aging-like skin atrophy via antioxidant activity in mice. *PLoS One*. 2014 Oct 15;9(10):e109288. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0109288. PMID: 25333617; PMID: PMC4198089.
25. Satoshi Kawakami, Hiroyuki Ichikawa, Tsutomu Sato, Hiroki Kataoka, Takaharu Ide, Hayato Terayama, Kou Sakabe. Antioxidant ability of platinum-palladium-Study using soft drinks containing platinum-palladium. *Journal of the Japan Society for Oral Functional Water*. 2021;22(1):3-9.
26. Yang B, Chen Y, Shi J. Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS)-Based Nanomedicine. *Chem Rev*. 2019 Apr 24;119(8):4881-4985. doi: 10.1021/acs.chemrev.8b00626. Epub 2019 Apr 11. PMID: 30973011.
27. Binks SP, Dobrota M. Kinetics and mechanism of uptake of platinum-based pharmaceuticals by the rat small intestine. *Biochem Pharmacol*. 1990 Sep 15;40(6):1329-36. doi: 10.1016/0006-2952(90)90400-f. PMID: 2206139.
28. Sable V, Maindan K, Kapdi AR, Shejwalkar PS, Hara K. Active Palladium Colloids via Palladacycle Degradation as Efficient Catalysts for Oxidative Homocoupling and Cross-Coupling of Aryl Boronic Acids. *ACS Omega*. 2017 Jan 24;2(1):204-217. doi: 10.1021/acsomega.6b00326. PMID: 31457222; PMID: PMC6641007.
29. Zhang WZ, Venardos K, Chin-Dusting J, Kaye DM. Adverse effects of cigarette smoke on NO bioavailability: role of arginine metabolism and oxidative stress. *Hypertension*. 2006 Aug;48(2):278-85. doi: 10.1161/01.HYP.0000231509.27406.42. Epub 2006 Jun 26. PMID: 16801489.
30. Mittler R. ROS Are Good. *Trends Plant Sci*. 2017 Jan;22(1):11-19. doi: 10.1016/j.tplants.2016.08.002. Epub 2016 Sep 23. PMID: 27666517.
31. Liguori I, Russo G, Curcio F, Bulli G, Aran L, Della-Morte D, Gargiulo G, Testa G, Cacciatore F, Bonaduce D, Abete P. Oxidative stress, aging, and diseases. *Clin Interv Aging*. 2018 Apr 26;13:757-772. doi: 10.2147/CIA.S158513. PMID: 29731617; PMID: PMC5927356.
32. Carling D. AMPK signalling in health and disease. *Curr Opin Cell Biol*. 2017 Apr;45:31-37. doi: 10.1016/j.ceb.2017.01.005. Epub 2017 Feb 21. PMID: 28232179.
33. Boyer PD, Chance B, Ernster L, Mitchell P, Racker E, Slater EC. Oxidative phosphorylation and photophosphorylation. *Annu Rev Biochem*. 1977;46:955-66. doi: 10.1146/annurev.bi.46.070177.004515. PMID: 18361775.
34. Cool B, Zinker B, Chiou W, Kifle L, Cao N, Perham M, Dickinson R, Adler A, Gagne G, Iyengar R, Zhao G, Marsh K, Kym P, Jung P, Camp HS, Frevert E. Identification and characterization of a small molecule AMPK activator that treats key components of type 2 diabetes and the metabolic syndrome. *Cell Metab*. 2006 Jun;3(6):403-16. doi: 10.1016/j.cmet.2006.05.005. PMID: 16753576.
35. Giordanetto F, Karis D. Direct AMP-activated protein kinase activators: a review of evidence from the patent literature. *Expert Opin Ther Pat*. 2012 Dec;22(12):1467-77. doi: 10.1517/13543776.2012.743994. Epub 2012 Nov 8. PMID: 23136886.
36. Xiao B, Sanders MJ, Carmena D, Bright NJ, Haire LF, Underwood E, Patel BR, Heath RB, Walker PA, Hallen S, Giordanetto F, Martin SR, Carling D, Gamblin SJ. Structural basis of AMPK regulation by small molecule activators. *Nat Commun*. 2013;4:3017. doi: 10.1038/ncomms4017. PMID: 24352254; PMID: PMC3905731.
37. Herzig S, Shaw RJ. AMPK: guardian of metabolism and mitochondrial homeostasis. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol*. 2018 Feb;19(2):121-135. doi: 10.1038/nrm.2017.95. Epub 2017 Oct 4. PMID: 28974774; PMID: PMC5780224.
38. Mihaylova MM, Shaw RJ. The AMPK signalling pathway coordinates cell growth, autophagy and metabolism. *Nat Cell Biol*. 2011 Sep 2;13(9):1016-23. doi: 10.1038/ncb2329. PMID: 21892142; PMID: PMC3249400.
39. Russell FM, Hardie DG. AMP-Activated Protein Kinase: Do We Need Activators or Inhibitors to Treat or Prevent Cancer? *Int J Mol Sci*. 2020 Dec 27;22(1):186. doi: 10.3390/ijms22010186. PMID: 33375416; PMID: PMC7795930.
40. Wu S, Zou MH. AMPK, Mitochondrial Function, and Cardiovascular Disease. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2020 Jul 15;21(14):4987. doi: 10.3390/ijms21144987. PMID: 32679729; PMID: PMC7404275.

41. Zhang D, Wang W, Sun X, Xu D, Wang C, Zhang Q, Wang H, Luo W, Chen Y, Chen H, Liu Z. AMPK regulates autophagy by phosphorylating BECN1 at threonine 388. *Autophagy*. 2016 Sep;12(9):1447-59. doi: 10.1080/15548627.2016.1185576. Epub 2016 Jun 15. PMID: 27304906; PMCID: PMC5082788.
42. Bergeron R, Ren JM, Cadman KS, Moore IK, Perret P, Pypaert M, Young LH, Semenkovich CF, Shulman GI. Chronic activation of AMP kinase results in NRF-1 activation and mitochondrial biogenesis. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab*. 2001 Dec;281(6):E1340-6. doi: 10.1152/ajpendo.2001.281.6.E1340. PMID: 11701451.
43. Hwang JH, Kim YH, Noh JR, Choi DH, Kim KS, Lee CH. Enhanced Production of Adenosine Triphosphate by Pharmacological Activation of Adenosine Monophosphate-Activated Protein Kinase Ameliorates Acetaminophen-Induced Liver Injury. *Mol Cells*. 2015 Oct;38(10):843-50. doi: 10.14348/molcells.2015.0072. Epub 2015 Oct 2. PMID: 26434492; PMCID: PMC4625065.
44. Hardie DG, Schaffer BE, Brunet A. AMPK: An Energy-Sensing Pathway with Multiple Inputs and Outputs. *Trends Cell Biol*. 2016 Mar;26(3):190-201. doi: 10.1016/j.tcb.2015.10.013. Epub 2015 Nov 23. PMID: 26616193; PMCID: PMC5881568.
45. Cheng XY, Li YY, Huang C, Li J, Yao HW. AMP-activated protein kinase reduces inflammatory responses and cellular senescence in pulmonary emphysema. *Oncotarget*. 2017 Apr 4;8(14):22513-22523. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.15116. PMID: 28186975; PMCID: PMC5410241.

How to cite this article: Kawakami S, Shirakawa T, Sakabe K, Sato T, Ide T, Wajima S, Suma R, Fukuzawa Y. Drinking Water Containing Platinum-Palladium (Functional Nutrient Water) Improved Interstitial Pneumonia and COPD: A Case Report. *J Biomed Res Environ Sci*. 2022 June 10; 3(6): 687-693. doi: 10.37871/jbres1498, Article ID: JBRES1498, Available at: <https://www.jelsciences.com/articles/jbres1498.pdf>